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A CLINICAL STUDY TO COMPARE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VENLAFAXINE, BUPROPION WITH AMITRIPTYLINE IN DIABETIC NEUROPATHIC PAIN

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ABSTRACT

Present study was undertaken to compare the effectiveness of venlafaxine, bupropion with amitriptyline in diabetic neuropathic pain. This was an open, parallel, prospective and randomized type study conducted at the outpatient departments of medicine and neurology of Era's Lucknow Medical College & Hospital, Lucknow and Chhatrapati Shahuji Maharaj Medical University, Lucknow, respectively, to compare the effects of venlafaxine, bupropion and amitriptyline in patients suffering from diabetic neuropathic pain. Present study gives following conclusions: 1). Pain scores improvement (decrease) was highest in amitriptyline followed by venlafaxine followed by bupropion. 2). QOL scores improvement (decrease) was highest in venlafaxine followed by bupropion and least in amitriptyline. 3). NCVs (m/s) improvement (increase) was highest in amitriptyline in all the studied nerves except RCPN. 4). In RCPN, the NCV (m/s) improvement (increase) was highest in venlafaxine followed by bupropion followed by amitriptyline.

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Introduction

Neuropathic pain as the definition of International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) is the pain associated with a lesion, trauma or dysfunction of somatosensory nervous system (central or peripheral) ^(1,2,3). Various conditions can affect nerves and may cause neuropathic pain. These include trigeminal neuralgia, post herpetic neuralgia (pain following shingles), diabetic neuropathy, phantom limb pain following an amputation, multiple sclerosis, pain following chemotherapy and pain due to alcoholism and vitamin deficiencies. The prevalence of pain is indicated to be 10-20% in diabetic patients and 40-50% in part of them with diabetic neuropathy ^(4,5,6,7,8,9). Diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) is one of the most common complications of diabetes mellitus. There is no doubt that the rate of diabetes in people is increasing and the new data indicate that industrialization and environmental pollution expand the problem ⁽¹⁰⁾.

Neuropathic pain clearly can impact a patient's ability to carry out his or her activities of daily living (ADLs). Pain relief is important to improve the patient's quality of life (QOL). Although a goal of 100% pain relief is ideal, in reality many patients achieve no more than 30% to 50% pain reduction. This is where measurements of function play a role because for many patients, that amount of relief may translate to an ability to return to work or social activities and thus vastly improve their quality of life and mood. Several agents have been used with varying degree of success in the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain including nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), topical agents, opioid analgesics, antiarrhythmics, N-methyl D-aspartate (NMDA) antagonists, antiepileptics and antidepressants (both tricyclic antidepressants and serotonin reuptake inhibitors). The tricyclic antidepressants are considered first line systemic therapy for many neuropathic pain syndromes, including diabetic neuropathy ⁽¹¹⁾. Amitriptyline was the first tricyclic used to treat neuropathy and it is still widely prescribed. It is a balanced serotonin and nor adrenaline reuptake inhibitor. It also blocks α -adrenergic, histaminergic, muscarinic cholinergic and NMDA receptors ⁽¹²⁾. Amitriptyline role in pain modulation correlates its ability to increase the amount of circulating inhibitory pain neurotransmitters nor adrenaline and serotonin through reuptake inhibition ^(13,14). The utility of amitriptyline in the treatment of PDN is limited by its tolerability. Due to unfavorable side-effects, non-tolerability and negative influence on QOL researchers have turned to newer classes of antidepressants for the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain like venlafaxine & bupropion. Though, these are safe and effective as antidepressants and widely prescribed for this purpose but limited studies have shown their efficacy in the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain without any clear-cut conclusion. Venlafaxine, a chemically novel antidepressant, has demonstrated effectiveness in the treatment of pain associated with diabetic peripheral neuropathy in several case reports ^(15,16). It increases serotonin, nor adrenaline and to some extent dopamine levels in synaptic cleft by blocking the reuptake of these neurotransmitters. It appears to have a favorable drug interaction profile and warrants further study in treating pain associated with diabetic peripheral neuropathy ⁽¹⁷⁾.

Bupropion is an atypical antidepressant that acts as a norepinephrine and dopamine reuptake inhibitor. Randomized double-blind study with neuropathic pain found that 150 mg of bupropion sustained release (SR) was significantly better than placebo in reducing pain intensity; three out of four patients experienced pain relief while on active treatment ⁽¹⁸⁾. Side effects were rated as mild. Larger and longer trials are required to confirm the efficacy of bupropion in DPN. The present study aimed at evaluating better treatment with efficacy, better safety profile and positive impact in quality of life in patients of diabetic neuropathic pain. The objective of this study was to assess and compare the effects of venlafaxine, bupropion and amitriptyline in patients suffering from diabetic neuropathic pain.

Material & Methods

Study design

This was an open, parallel, prospective and randomized type study conducted at the outpatient departments of medicine and neurology of Era's Lucknow Medical College & Hospital, Lucknow and Chhatrapati Shahuji Maharaj Medical University, Lucknow, respectively, to compare the effects of venlafaxine, bupropion and amitriptyline in patients suffering from diabetic neuropathic pain. The total duration of the study was 18 months.

Eligibility of patients

The clinical criteria for the diagnosis of diabetic neuropathy were accordingly as recommended by Dyck⁽²²⁾ and Pascuzzi⁽²³⁾. Possibility of neuropathy due to other causes was excluded by clinical history, clinical examination and investigations of the patients.

Parameters of study

(A) Visual analog scale (VAS) is commonly used to describe the intensity of pain or how much pain the patient is feeling. It is a straight line with left end of the line representing no pain (pain score 0) and right end of the line representing the worst possible pain (pain score 10). The patients are asked to mark on the line where the pain is in relation to the two extremes and in this way pain scores are given to the patients⁽¹⁹⁾.

(B) Brief pain inventory (BPI) includes questions which assess the effect of pain on quality of life and interference with daily activities⁽²⁰⁾. It uses 7 items to assess interference with activities of daily life (general activity, mood, walking ability, normal work, relations with others, sleep, and enjoyment of life). Each question uses an 11-point interference scale (0 indicating no interference and 10 indicating complete interference). Patient is asked to encircle on each scale according to their perception in past 24 hours. Item scores from 0 to 3 suggest mild interference, whereas scores from 4 to 6 suggest moderate interference and those 7 or higher suggest severe interference⁽²¹⁾. After completing all the scales we took the mean of all the parameters by adding the scores and dividing them by 7. This mean score of BPI was later on used for statistical comparisons. **(C) Nerve conduction velocity (NCV)** is a test of the speed of electrical signals through a nerve. The test is performed by electrical stimulation of a peripheral nerve and recording from a muscle supplied by this nerve. The nerve's resulting electrical activity is recorded by the other electrodes. The distance between electrodes and the time it takes for electrical impulses to travel between electrodes are used to determine the speed of the nerve signals. The distance is measured in millimeters (mm) and the time is measured in milliseconds (ms). The NCV is expressed as meter/seconds (m/s).

Initial evaluation

The patients were included in the study after proper diagnosis and fulfilling the inclusion/exclusion criteria with informed consent. A standardized initial evaluation, which included a complete clinical history, clinical examination, investigations, assessment of pain by VAS and assessment of QOL by BPI, was done at the time of 1st visit (day 0). Patients having pain score less than 4 were excluded from the study. At the same time nerve conduction velocity (NCV) study of ulnar, median, common peroneal and posterior tibial nerves of right side was done. The machine which we used for NCV study was Neuro Perfect, manufactured by Medic aid system-Chandigarh.

Treatment groups with drug studied and Rescue therapy

Eligible patients fulfilling the mentioned criteria were randomized by card method into three treatment groups (Groups A, B and C) depending on the drugs prescribed. In Group A, eligible 34 patients (20 males and 14 females) were given tablet amitriptyline, 25 mg once after meal at night for 2 months. In Group B, eligible 31 patients (18 males and 13 females) were given capsule venlafaxine, 75 mg once after meal at night for 2 months. In Group C, eligible 30 patients (22 males and 8 females) of group C were given tablet bupropion, 150 mg once after meal at night for 2 months. And tablet paracetamol 500 mg was allowed as rescue therapy if patient felt inadequate relief of pain by the medication.

Follow-ups for clinical assessment

Patients were requested to come after 1 month and again the same assessment of pain by VAS, assessment of QOL by BPI and NCV study were done at the IInd visit. Repetition of the same work was done after 1 month more at the IIIrd visit.

Outcome measures

Comparison of responses obtained by group A (amitriptyline), group B (venlafaxine) and group C (bupropion) on day 0, after 1 month and after 2 months were done within the groups and in between the groups. There were two types of comparisons: **1- Intra group's comparison** (within A, B and C groups): Visit I (day 0) versus Visit II (after 1 month); Visit I (day 0) versus Visit III (after 2 months); Visit II (after 1 month) versus Visit III (after 2 months); and **2-Inter group's comparison** (in between A, B and C groups): Visit I (amitriptyline) versus Visit I (venlafaxine); Visit I (amitriptyline) versus Visit I (bupropion); Visit I (venlafaxine) versus Visit I (bupropion). Comparisons were done in the same way within the IInd and IIIrd visits of the patients in between A, B and C groups.

Statistical analysis

Data were summarized as Mean \pm SE. Groups were compared by using repeated measures one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Newman-Keuls post hoc test. Homogeneity of variance was tested by Hartley F-max, Cochran C and Bartlett chi-square (χ^2) tests. A two-tailed ($\alpha=2$) probability $p<0.05$ was considered to be statistically significant. All analyses were performed on STATISTICA (version 6.0) while graphs were done on Graph Pad Prism (version 3.0). For each treatment, a percent mean change (from initial to final or final to initial) was also calculated as

$$\% \text{ change} = \frac{\text{Mean}_1 - \text{Mean}_2}{\text{Mean}_1} \times 100$$

where, Mean ₁ > Mean ₂ and, Mean ₁: Mean of Ist group & Mean ₂: Mean of IInd group.

Fig 1: Flow Chart of study

Results

A-Assessment of pain (by VAS)

The pain scores (by VAS) of three treatment groups were summarized and shown graphically by Fig. 1. In all three groups, the mean pain scores decrease with the time (in months) and the decrease was evident highest in amitriptyline (49.4%) followed by venlafaxine (36.7%) and least in bupropion (16.7%) (Fig.1). When the mean pain scores compared between the treatments, the mean pain scores in all three groups at day 0 and after 1 month were found to be the same ($p>0.05$) while they differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$) between the treatments after 2 months. Similarly, comparing the mean pain scores between the periods, the mean pain scores in all three groups differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$) except in bupropion at day 0 vs. after 1 month.

B- Assessment of Quality of Life (by BPI)

The quality of life (QOL) scores (by BPI) of three treatment groups were summarized. In all three groups, the mean QOL scores decrease (improvement) with the time (in months) and the decrease was evident highest in venlafaxine (46.3%) followed by bupropion (33.2%) and least in amitriptyline (29.1%). Comparing the mean QOL scores between the treatments, the mean QOL scores in all three groups at day 0 were found to be the same ($p>0.05$) while they differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$) after 1 month and after 2 months of

treatments except in amitriptyline vs. bupropion after 2 months. Similarly, comparing the mean QOL scores between the periods, the mean QOL scores in all three groups differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$).

Fig. 1: Mean (± SE) pain scores (by VAS) of three groups.

C- Nerve conduction velocity (NCV) study

1-RUN (Right ulnar nerve)

The NCVs (m/s) of RUNs of three treatment groups were summarized. In all three groups, the mean NCVs (m/s) increase with the time (in months) and the increase was evident highest in amitriptyline (3.6%) followed by venlafaxine (2.5%) and least in bupropion (1.2%). Comparing the mean NCVs (m/s) between the treatments, the mean NCVs (m/s) in all three groups at day 0 and after 1 month were found to be the same ($p>0.05$) while after 2 months they differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$) between amitriptyline vs. bupropion and between venlafaxine vs. bupropion. Similarly, comparing the mean NCVs (m/s) of RUNs between the periods, the mean NCVs (m/s) in all three groups differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$) except in bupropion at day 0 vs. after 1 month.

2. RMN (Right median nerve)

The NCVs (m/s) of RMNs of three treatment groups were summarized. In all three groups, the mean NCVs (m/s) increase with the time (in months) and the increase was evident highest in amitriptyline (3.5%) followed by venlafaxine (2.3%) and least in bupropion (1.2%). Comparing the mean NCVs(m/s) of RMNs between the treatments, the mean NCVs(m/s) in all three groups at day 0 and after 1 month were found to be the same ($p>0.05$) while after 2 months they differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$) between amitriptyline vs. venlafaxine and between amitriptyline vs. bupropion. Similarly, comparing the mean NCVs (m/s) of RMNs between the periods, the mean NCVs (m/s) in all three groups differed significantly ($p<0.01$) except in venlafaxine and in bupropion at day 0 vs. after 1 month.

3. RCPN (Right common peroneal nerve)

The NCVs (m/s) of RCPNs of three treatment groups were summarized. In all three groups, the mean NCVs(m/s) increase with the time (in months) and the increase was evident highest in venlafaxine (14.4%) followed by bupropion (13.1%) and least in amitriptyline (12.7%). Comparing the mean NCVs (m/s) of RCPNs between the treatments, the mean NCVs (m/s) in all three groups at all periods were found to be the same ($p>0.05$). Similarly, comparing the mean NCVs (m/s) of RCPNs between the periods, the mean NCVs (m/s) in all three groups differed significantly ($p<0.01$) except at day 0 vs. after 1 month.

4. RPTN (Right posterior tibial nerve)

The NCVs (m/s) of RPTNs of three treatment groups were summarized. In all three groups, the mean NCVs (m/s) increase with the time (in months) and the increase was evident highest in amitriptyline (5.6%) followed by venlafaxine (2.7%) and least in bupropion (1.0%). Comparing the mean NCVs (m/s) of RPTNs between the treatments, the mean NCVs (m/s) in all three groups at day 0 and after 1 month were found to be the same ($p>0.05$) while after 2 months they differed significantly ($p<0.05$ or $p<0.01$) between amitriptyline vs. venlafaxine and between amitriptyline vs. bupropion. Similarly, comparing the mean NCVs (m/s) of RPTNs between the periods, the mean NCVs(m/s) in all three groups differed significantly ($p<0.01$) except in venlafaxine at day 0 vs. after 1 month and in bupropion at day 0 vs. after 1 month and after 1 month vs. after 2 months.

Discussion

Approximately 50% of patients who have had diabetes for more than 25 years will develop neuropathy and will have pain as a symptom of neuropathy. Neuropathy is usually a late finding in type 1 diabetes; however, it can be an early finding in type 2 diabetes. The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT) showed that tight glycemic control will reduce the incidence of neuropathy by 60%. Although a goal of 100% pain relief is ideal, in reality many patients achieve no more than 30% to 50% pain reduction. This is where measurements of function play a role because for many patients, that amount of relief may translate to an ability to return to work or social activities and thus vastly improve their quality of life and mood. As with other chronic pain states, it is important for the physician and patient to set and assess goals together, and physicians must keep in mind that patients' goals for treatment and perception of relief may differ from their own. This study provides an overview of pharmacologic options for the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain. Although it is well established that the combination of non-pharmacologic methods with medication are required in order to achieve adequate pain relief. This discussion is limited to the efficacy, safety and tolerability of medications specially approved for the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain. The standard treatment for PDN for years had been tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs). TCAs are considered first-line systemic therapy for many neuropathic pain syndromes, including diabetic neuropathy. Their role in pain modulation correlates with their ability to increase the amount of circulating inhibitory pain neurotransmitters, nor adrenaline and serotonin, through reuptake inhibition. They act centrally to reduce the perception of pain. In summarizing the trials performed for the treatment of PDN with TCAs, 30% of patients obtain 50% pain relief. They also block α adrenergic, histaminergic, muscarinic cholinergic, and NMDA receptors. The adverse effects of TCAs are fairly predictable and mostly anticholinergic in nature which includes dry mouth, constipation, dizziness, blurred vision, cardiac arrhythmias and urinary retention. The tertiary amine TCAs are associated with more severe effects, including extreme sedation and orthostatic hypotension, limiting their usefulness in many patients. TCA use should be avoided in patients with second-degree or third-degree heart block, arrhythmias, prolonged QT interval on the

electrocardiogram, severe liver disease, and in patients who have had a recent acute myocardial infarction. Amitriptyline has the highest affinity for the muscarinic receptors which causes unwanted side effects like sedation, dry mouth, blurred vision and urinary retention. It is contraindicated for older patients and patients with any cardiovascular disease because it has been shown to prolong QT intervals. The utility of amitriptyline in the treatment of PDN is limited by its tolerability. Due to these unfavorable side-effects, non-tolerability and negative influence on QOL newer classes of antidepressants are required for the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain like venlafaxine & bupropion. Though, these are safe and effective as antidepressants but limited studies have shown their efficacy in the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain without any clear-cut conclusion. Venlafaxine, unlike other drugs which also block the uptake of nor adrenaline and serotonin, it does not interact with cholinergic, adrenergic or histaminergic receptors and therefore, does not produce the usual side effects of tricyclic group of antidepressant drugs. Common side effects like irritability, insomnia, dizziness, tremor, anorexia, somnolence, sweating and hypertension may occur rarely and of mild severity. It appears to have a favorable drug interaction profile and warrants further study in treating pain associated with DPN. Bupropion unlike TCAs, it does appear to pose the threat of causing irregular heartbeats in cardiac patients. Larger and longer trials are required to confirm the efficacy of bupropion in DPN. The present study aimed at evaluating antidepressant drugs with more efficacy, lesser toxicity, better tolerability and improved QOL. The objective of this study was to assess and compare the effects of venlafaxine, bupropion and amitriptyline in patients suffering from diabetic neuropathic pain.

Comparative improvement (decrease) in pain scores

Regarding the pain assessment by VAS in all the three groups, the mean pain scores decrease with the time (in months) and this improvement (decrease) was evident highest in amitriptyline (49.4%) followed by venlafaxine (36.7%) and least in bupropion (16.7%). Because neuropathic pain involves variety of neurotransmitters and multiple possible mechanisms for its production. It may be explained that why amitriptyline gave the best results regarding decrease in pain scores. Amitriptyline is a serotonin and nor epinephrine reuptake inhibitor. It also blocks α adrenergic, histaminergic, muscarinic cholinergic and NMDA receptors and has been able to reduce the pain perception remarkably. But the action over these receptors also produces several side effects and makes this drug intolerable to the patients. Venlafaxine, on the other hand, is more selective serotonin and nor epinephrine reuptake inhibitor and does not interact with other receptors. This may be the possible reason for its effect in reducing pain scores less in comparison to amitriptyline. But because of its selectivity over these receptors and no interaction with other receptors, its side-effect profile is also less in comparison to amitriptyline. At the last, bupropion, as shown by the study, is least effective and this may be due to its selectivity over nor epinephrine and dopamine receptors. Its side-effect profile is also less in comparison to amitriptyline because of no interaction with other receptors.

Comparative improvement (decrease) in quality of life (QOL) scores

Regarding the QOL assessment by BPI, which is a well recommended and authentic questionnaire, in all the three groups, the mean QOL scores decrease with the time (in months) and this improvement (decrease) was evident highest in venlafaxine (46.3%) followed by bupropion (33.2%) and least in amitriptyline (29.1%). We found that during the Ist visit (day 0) most of the patients were having compromised QOL as shown by higher scores. During the IInd and IIIrd visits the scores were significantly reduced in patients with venlafaxine and bupropion. The explanation for this significant reduction in QOL scores in these two groups may be because of their no interaction with other receptors and low index of side effect profiles. Regarding amitriptyline, we got surprised results during the assessment QOL, because we were hoping the best results from this drug on the

basis of results obtained from analysis of pain scores by VAS, but after the comparison and statistical analysis we found very less improvement (decrease) in QOL scores in patients treated with amitriptyline. This may be because of its action over different receptors which have produced multiple side effects including sedation and hampering the QOL.

Comparative improvement (increase) in NCVs (m/s)

Regarding NCV study, the results show that NCVs (m/s) improvement (increase) was evident highest in amitriptyline followed by venlafaxine and least in bupropion, in all the studied nerves except RCPN. The explanation for this improvement (increase) in NCVs (m/s) may be same as for the improvement (decrease) of pain scores by VAS. However, the explanation why amitriptyline did not produce maximum improvement (increase) in NCV (m/s) in RCPN still remains the topic for controversy. Further research regarding the NCV study may be planned to confirm these results and find out possible explanation.

Conclusion

Present study was an open, parallel, prospective and randomized type. It gives following conclusions: 1). Pain scores improvement (decrease) was highest in amitriptyline followed by venlafaxine followed by bupropion. 2). QOL scores improvement (decrease) was highest in venlafaxine followed by bupropion and least in amitriptyline. 3). NCVs (m/s) improvement (increase) was highest in amitriptyline in all the studied nerves except RCPN. 4). In RCPN, the NCV (m/s) improvement (increase) was highest in venlafaxine followed by bupropion followed by amitriptyline. The final conclusion of this study is that though, amitriptyline is more efficacious in reducing the pain but did not improved QOL as compared to other two drugs used in the study. Its action over other receptors produces several side effects and makes this drug not a favorable choice for physicians. There is need for better drugs which can reduce the pain, improve QOL and having low index of side effect profile. On the other hand, venlafaxine though, reduced less pain than amitriptyline but significantly improved QOL as compared to other two drugs used in the study. It also has low index of side-effect profile and can be very well recommended as a better drug for the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain However, more studies with more number of patients are needed to give more strength to the conclusion of the present study. At the last, bupropion, as shown by the study, is least effective in reducing pain and in between the other two drugs in improving QOL. It also has low index of side effect profile and whenever venlafaxine is not acceptable by the patients or patients allergic to venlafaxine, it can be used as monotherapy for the treatment of diabetic neuropathic pain. Whenever the pain is severe and does not controlled with venlafaxine, amitriptyline can be recommended if the patients do not have any significant contraindication.

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